

CONDITIONS OF VERTICAL MIGRATIONS OF KRILL IN ANTARCTIC PENINSULA WATERS (FAO SUBAREA 48.1)

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The abstract provides the author's research on the spatio-temporal processes of vertical migration (diel vertical migration – DVM) of Antarctic krill under the influence of endogenous circadian rhythms based on catch data from 822 trawls in the subarea of the Antarctic Peninsula in March-June 2017. The DVM of krill is considered in relation to the characteristics of its biology, the size of catches, and the sea surface temperature (SST), at fishing horizons in the fishing environment of the Ukrainian RKTS vessel "*More Sodruzhestva*".

DVM allowed to reveal their complex structure. Acoustic observations indicate that krill DVM is represented by the main 24-hour component (night – upward movement, day – downward movement) and a smaller 12-hour component (repeated increase in the middle of the day), dependent, among other things, on the duration of daylight. Their amplitudes under conditions of high food availability are insignificant but increase as the concentration of food decreases from March to June, including the factor of critical temperatures, undoubtedly influencing its life cycle.

Studies of the thermal structure of waters in the autumn-winter period under conditions of ongoing cooling and convective mixing of waters showed the following features that affected DVM:

- in March, with relatively warm conditions in the atmosphere and in the water layer from the surface to the lower horizons of the catch, a quasi-homogeneous layer with temperature variability of up to 0.3 °C was observed with higher values closer to the surface.

- in April-June, with increased cooling of the surface layer and convection, the temperature of the water layer to the lower horizons of the catch gradually decreased, reaching record negative values in June in the central part of the strait (up to minus 2.1 °C). At the same time, from the second ten-day period of April, the subsurface layers became warmer, especially in the eastern part of the strait, where the difference in SST and the temperature of the horizons of the catch reached 1.0 °C.

Transformations of the thermal structure of waters, in combination with other factors, affected the characteristics of krill migrations, demonstrating a tendency to deepen from March to June. Thus, in March, the average value of the krill localization horizon was 21 m, in April 52 m, in May 87 m, and in June 91 m, where changes in the food spectrum (transition from phytoplanktonic to zooplanktonic organisms), a decrease in food supply and filling of stomachs were noted.

The practical significance of our study is the identification of vertical amplitude fluctuations of krill aggregations at the daily and intersessional levels. Evidence of their deepening is reflected in an increase in the time of setting and hauling the trawl from 10–20 minutes at the beginning of the fishery and up to 30–50 minutes at the stages of its completion at greater depths. This circumstance, in combination with other factors, must be taken into account when planning and implementing a krill fishery strategy in order to achieve its efficiency and profitability, taking into account the gross operating profit of 152 million US dollars (according to data for 2019).